

Research on the Construction and Application of Teaching Quality Monitoring and Evaluation System of Law Major in Colleges and Universities

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ABSTRACT

Teaching quality is the core of the development of law education in Colleges and universities, and the lifeline of law education in Colleges and universities. It is very important to improve the teaching quality of law education in Colleges and universities to improve the monitoring system of teaching quality. In order to construct a scientific, reasonable and effective teaching quality monitoring system, we should take the modern education concept as the guidance, the system construction as the foundation, and the effective information feedback as the foundation, establish and improve the teaching management system which is suitable for the modern teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system, so as to effectively guarantee the lasting improvement of the teaching quality of law in Colleges and universities. To strengthen the supervision of teaching quality in Colleges and universities, with the improvement of teaching quality as the core and the cultivation of high-quality applied talents as the goal, we should reasonably organize the activities and functions of all links and departments in the teaching process, form an organic whole with clear tasks, responsibilities and authorities, which can coordinate and promote each other, and form a long-term operation of the supervision and evaluation of law teaching quality in Colleges and universities Line mechanism.

KEYWORDS: Law major; Teaching quality monitoring; Teaching quality evaluation; Feedback and processing mechanism

I. INTRODUCTION

Education quality monitoring and evaluation can not only dynamically monitor the real state of education and teaching, scientifically inspect the actual learning effect of students, comprehensively evaluate the working state and teaching attitude of teachers, but also scientifically measure the actual teaching level, teaching effect and overall quality of each teacher [1]. How to train legal talents has become an important issue in the reform, construction and development of law education. Its effective solution is to establish a set of quality monitoring system of law education with the functions of guidance and encouragement, feedback and communication, inspection and monitoring, so as to make the law education on the road of healthy, orderly and efficient development. Some scholars think that with the rapid development of law education in Colleges and universities, the problems in the teaching mode of understanding the meaning of legal provisions and imparting legal knowledge are gradually highlighted, which leads to social doubts on the undergraduate teaching of law. Law education is still in the exploratory stage, so we need to establish a set of scientific and reasonable teaching quality monitoring system, to stabilize the starting point and specification of law education, through the operation of teaching quality monitoring system, to form a virtuous cycle

mechanism of construction, evaluation and reform, to promote the continuous development of law education in Colleges and universities in the process of reflection and reconstruction, and to seek for a system that is in line with China's national conditions The mode and way of law education. Under the supervision of teaching quality, modern law education needs to promote construction, reform and management by evaluation, so as to encourage the construction and development of law education in Colleges and universities, and promote the development of law education towards modernization. Teaching quality monitoring and evaluation is the guarantee of improving teaching quality. At present, most of the teaching quality monitoring and evaluation in Colleges and universities still adopt the traditional mode, there are many problems, which affect the reliability and validity of the monitoring and evaluation. Only by combining the characteristics of colleges and universities to build a scientific and reasonable teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system, can we achieve the goal of accurate teaching quality monitoring and evaluation. The internal teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system is an important guarantee for the school to continuously improve the quality of education. Three levels of supervision, supervision and evaluation of teaching,

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teachers' evaluation of learning, and social evaluation of school constitute the internal teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of colleges and universities.

Strengthening the construction of quality monitoring and evaluation system of law major is the need of implementing the national medium and long-term education reform and development plan. The outline of the national medium and long term education reform and development plan (2010-2020) makes a detailed plan for the reform and development of higher education, and clearly points out that the key point of China's higher education reform is to improve the quality of higher education and personnel training. From the macro level, to improve the quality of personnel training is not only the need of higher education's own development law, but also the need to run a satisfactory higher education for the people, improve the ability of students' employment and entrepreneurship, and also the need to build an innovative country and a socialist harmonious society. Strengthening the construction of quality monitoring and evaluation system of law major is the need to improve the quality of law major personnel training. In terms of the current situation and future trend of talent training in Colleges and universities, improving the quality of talent training in Colleges and universities has become one of the main tasks of future reform in Colleges and universities. The first task to improve the quality of personnel training in Colleges and universities is to establish the quality standard of personnel, monitor and evaluate it, find the gap between the current situation of personnel training and the goal of personnel training, then reform the existing mode of personnel training, improve the quality of personnel training, and finally realize the goal of personnel training. Strengthening the construction of quality monitoring and evaluation system of law major is the need to promote the comprehensive development of law major students. From the perspective of social needs and students' own development, at present, the society has higher and higher requirements for talents, which not only requires the talents trained in Colleges and universities to have solid professional basic knowledge, but also hopes that the talents trained in Colleges and universities can have various abilities, such as good innovation ability And communication skills. In order to meet the needs of talents in the future, the monitoring and evaluation of talents in various aspects can help students set up the goal of all-round development, and promote the multi-directional development of college students and the improvement of overall quality.

II. Guiding ideology, basic principles and important value of the construction of quality monitoring and evaluation system for talent training

The teaching work is the central work in the process of talent training of law school, and it is the basic way to cultivate talents and realize the educational purpose. Teaching quality is the lifeline of the survival and development of law school. We should promote the scientific and standardized management of teaching quality in law schools, improve the management level and teaching quality, and ensure the realization of talent training objectives.

A. Guiding ideology for the construction of quality monitoring and evaluation system of legal personnel training

Colleges and universities should adhere to the policy of "people-oriented, dynamic evaluation, prevention first,

prevention and control combined", based on the participation of the whole staff, based on various quality standards, with various evaluation as means, with the purpose of improving teaching quality, use systematic theories and methods to reasonably organize the quality management functions and activities of all stages, links and departments of teaching management To form an organic whole with clear tasks, responsibilities and authorities, which is coordinated and promoted each other, and strive to realize the comprehensiveness, wholeness and whole process of quality evaluation.

B. Basic principles for the construction of quality monitoring and evaluation system of legal personnel training

1. Adhere to the principle of comprehensive, objective, open and fair

The teaching quality control of law school must run through the whole process of teaching management and cover all aspects of teaching work. Taking classroom teaching quality monitoring as the center, classroom teaching is the key link of teaching work and the key point of all teaching monitoring work. Adopt scientific monitoring means to actively encourage all teachers, students and other personnel to participate in teaching monitoring.

2. Adhere to the principle of authority

Law school attaches great importance to the construction of teaching quality monitoring system and establishes a special quality evaluation system. The authority of the quality evaluation results can make the quality evaluation give full play to the guiding role, truly stimulate the work enthusiasm and initiative of leaders and teachers at all levels, so as to promote the work of all functional departments and colleges, and finally achieve the purpose of ensuring and improving the teaching quality. We should pay attention to the prudence and immutability of the results of teaching quality evaluation, implement the one vote veto system of "teaching quality evaluation", and link the evaluation results with performance evaluation, teachers' Professional Title Evaluation and professional promotion.

3. Adhere to the principle of scientificity

There are many factors that affect the teaching quality of law major in law school, some of which are difficult to measure with data and quantitative indicators. Therefore, we should pay attention to science in formulating the standards and methods of teaching quality monitoring and evaluation. When formulating the specific indicators of monitoring and evaluation, we will combine qualitative and quantitative evaluation to make accurate and fuzzy quantitative complementary, and adopt the method of multi-channel monitoring and evaluation. The teaching quality monitoring system should pay attention to its operability, simplify and simplify. It not only embodies the idea of comprehensive monitoring, but also meets the requirements of economic applicability and easy operation, so as to ensure that the main body of the system is clear, the procedure is simple and the implementation is easy.

4. Adhere to the principle of combining college level monitoring with secondary college monitoring

The school of law is responsible for the formulation of the training plan of its major, the organization and arrangement of all teaching links, the implementation, management and assessment of all teaching tasks, the management of teaching, scientific research and students, the professional

construction, curriculum construction, teaching material construction, laboratory construction, teaching staff construction, teaching and research office and college construction of the unit, and the advancement of teachers' business Training, teaching level, teaching discipline, teaching attitude, teaching and other aspects of management. The teaching organization, implementation and management of law school play a decisive role. In order to ensure the smooth progress of the teaching work and the continuous improvement of the teaching quality, we should fully mobilize the enthusiasm of each teaching unit in running a school, enhance its consciousness and sense of responsibility in running a school, and give full play to its inherent potential.

C. The important value of the construction of the quality monitoring and evaluation system for the cultivation of legal talents

1. It is conducive to providing scientific basis and Countermeasures for the better construction of the teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law major in general colleges and universities

To strengthen and optimize the practical teaching of law major is the most important thing to improve the quality of legal talents training, promote the construction of a country ruled by law and the implementation of innovation and entrepreneurship strategy, while to build a scientific quality monitoring system of practical teaching is a direct and effective measure to improve the effect of practical teaching of law major [2]. The construction of the quality monitoring and evaluation system can promote the improvement of the teaching quality monitoring system and the improvement of the teaching quality of law major, and better accomplish the 13th five year plan goal of the construction of law major of law college. According to the training plan and requirements of law professionals, starting from the training objectives of law professionals in Colleges and universities, the construction of teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law majors is essential to improve the quality of law talents training, which is conducive to ensuring the quality of law professionals training and ensuring that law talents meet the quality standards of law teaching.

2. It is conducive to better guarantee the realization of the goal of excellent legal personnel training

The construction of the teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law major is of great theoretical and practical significance to ensure the implementation of the "excellent legal talent education and training plan", to form a legal talent training system with reasonable discipline settings and Chinese characteristics of legal education concept, and to cultivate a number of high-quality legal talents. The research and implementation of the teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law specialty is conducive to the better promotion of the training quality of legal talents, the improvement of the practical ability of legal talents, the enhancement of the training strength of application-oriented and compound legal talents, and the cultivation of a batch of excellent legal professional talents to meet the needs of national construction and enterprise development.

3. It is conducive to improving the teaching system and mechanism of law undergraduate

The construction of teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law major is conducive to

strengthening the monitoring and evaluation of practical teaching quality. To give full play to the educational function of the practical teaching base, enterprises and schools should work out the training objectives together, pay attention to the participation of enterprises in the teaching process, match the skill training with the requirements of post talents, match the training objectives with the employment standards, promote the deepening of the establishment of law major and the reform of professional teaching content, and improve the pertinence and effectiveness of legal talents training.

4. It is conducive to the organic combination of law teaching reform and student employment

The construction of the teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law specialty is conducive to solving the problem of the disconnection between the education of law talents and the demand of enterprise talents, and realizing the effective connection between the education concept, training mode and the demand of enterprise talents. The construction and operation of scientific teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system can effectively solve the problem of the disconnection between the cultivation of talents in Colleges and the needs of social enterprises, strengthen the mutual understanding and communication between students and enterprises, enhance the pertinence and practicability of the cultivation scheme and curriculum, so as to provide practical and compound legal talents for enterprises.

III. The core content and system composition of the construction of the quality monitoring system of talent training in law school

A. Core content of quality monitoring system design for talent training

The quality monitoring of personnel training is to evaluate, supervise and exert the effect on the quality system of personnel training purposefully, so as to make the quality of personnel training achieve the expected purpose. The system has the functions of teaching monitoring, evaluation and feedback, which determines the direction of the whole talent training process. It plays an important role in the monitoring and regulation of the whole process of legal professional training. The ultimate goal of establishing the quality monitoring mechanism of talent training is to find out the factors that affect the quality of talent training and put forward improvement measures through scientific evaluation of the quality of talent training, so as to continuously improve the quality of talent training. The quality monitoring system of talent training should at least include the professional orientation and training objectives, classroom teaching links (specifically including class opening, lesson preparation classroom teaching, teacher's question answering, homework correction, examination and marking score registration, etc.), experimental links, internship links, curriculum design links, graduation design links, etc. the quality of talent training in each of the above links is related to the University method Therefore, it is necessary to monitor and evaluate the whole process of legal personnel training.

1. The quality monitoring of talent training evaluates the construction of law major, curriculum and teaching materials

It mainly evaluates whether the establishment of law major and curriculum in the college is reasonable, whether the

formulation of teaching plan is scientific, and whether the training objectives, enrollment and employment meet the market demand.

2. The evaluation of the teaching reform and research of law major should be strengthen

Firstly, we should mainly evaluate whether the teaching reform measures of the college are effective, whether the school running conditions are improved, and to assess and evaluate the teaching and research papers. Secondly, strengthen the monitoring and evaluation of the daily teaching management of each college, such as whether there are teaching accidents and errors, whether the teaching materials are complete, and whether the teaching organization and arrangement are reasonable. It mainly evaluates the teaching discipline, teaching attitude and teaching quality of college teachers. To monitor and evaluate the development and construction of law laboratory, off campus practice base and practice teaching. It mainly monitors and evaluates the management of each college laboratory, the development and construction of laboratory, the rate of experiment output, the construction of off campus practice base and the quality of relevant practice teaching. Finally, we should strengthen the monitoring and evaluation of law students, such as students' learning state, style of study and so on.

B. Composition of quality monitoring system of talent training in law school

With the transformation of education concept as the guide, with the emphasis on strengthening the construction of specialty, curriculum, practical teaching and the reform of teaching methods and means, with the core of strengthening the construction of teaching staff and teaching management, with the main line of establishing and improving the teaching quality control system and teaching incentive mechanism, and with an eye to and serving the construction of diversified personnel training mode. Through the dynamic management of teaching quality, we can promote colleges and universities to adapt to the changes of social development, make rational and efficient use of various resources, and comprehensively improve the teaching quality of colleges and universities, so that law schools can gain advantages in the competition, and promote the reform and construction of law schools to deepen.

1. Objective system and key task list of talent training quality monitoring

a. Objective system of quality monitoring system construction

The main monitoring points are talent training target positioning, talent training mode, talent training program, discipline and professional transformation and development direction. Personnel training process system. The main monitoring points are the formulation and implementation of the syllabus, the selection of teaching materials, the allocation of teachers, the quality of classroom teaching, the quality of practical teaching, the reform of teaching contents and means, the assessment methods and the quality of test papers. Personnel training quality system. The main monitoring points are course qualification rate, award rate of various competitions, innovation ability and scientific research ability, graduation rate, degree granting rate, postgraduate entrance examination rate, employment rate, employment level, employer evaluation, etc.

b. List of key tasks for the construction of quality monitoring system

The first is to solve the problem of breaking through the combination of the teaching of legal professional knowledge and the training objective of applied talents. The traditional legal education pays attention to the instillation of theoretical knowledge and neglects the training of professional skills, which results in the typical phenomenon of "four heavy and four light", that is, attaching great importance to teachers' teaching and neglecting students' research; attaching great importance to learning results and neglecting learning process; attaching great importance to theoretical learning and neglecting practical application; attaching great importance to professional knowledge and neglecting comprehensive quality. The domestic legal education circle is generally aware of this problem, and has discussed the teaching reform, trying to combine the experimental teaching with the theoretical teaching of legal education mode [3]. To explore and operate the teaching quality monitoring system of law major, improve the teaching quality management system, and establish and promote the monitoring and evaluation system of law teaching quality. It is necessary to establish a set of application-oriented undergraduate legal talents with high quality, strong ability and practice, improve the quality monitoring and evaluation system of legal specialty, and further improve the quality of legal talents training.

The second is to solve and break through the problem of blind spots in the monitoring of classroom teaching quality. There is a certain blind spot in the operation of teaching quality monitoring of law undergraduate education. We need to give full play to the reflection, measurement and improvement of teaching methods and the goal of improving teaching effect of the monitoring and evaluation system of law teaching quality. To solve the problem that the evaluation results depend too much on the evaluation scores of students, to pay attention to the subjective factors and case factors in the evaluation, to study how to make the monitoring indicators more fair, to make scientific analysis of the evaluation results, to carry out timely and effective feedback and improvement, so as to solve the tendency that both universities and teachers pay too much attention to the evaluation results of teaching quality, and to build a comprehensive system of law teaching Quality monitoring and evaluation system.

The third is to solve and break through the problem of insufficient monitoring of teaching quality in practical teaching. The training of law major must attach importance to the training of applied legal talents, and the practical teaching work bears the important function of improving students' practical ability and professional skills. Law education should pay more attention to the training and training of students' practical ability on the basis of the teaching and explanation of law theoretical knowledge. It is necessary to establish and improve the monitoring and evaluation system of the teaching quality of practical teaching law, strengthen the monitoring of the teaching quality, build the main system of the comprehensive system, and constantly improve the effect of practical teaching. There is an urgent need to solve the problems of the lack of practical teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system is not comprehensive and scientific, establish practical and targeted practical teaching monitoring measures, and provide theoretical basis and measures to ensure.

The fourth is to solve and break through the problem of lagging behind in the concept of teaching quality monitoring. Compared with the famous legal teaching quality management concepts at home and abroad, the teaching quality monitoring concepts of law major in Colleges and universities are relatively lagging behind, which can not play the role of the legal teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system. Schools, teachers and students should form all-out efforts, attach great importance to the construction of teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law major education, recognize the significance and role of the construction of teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law, deepen the theoretical research and Discussion on the construction of teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law, establish a comprehensive and systematic scientific teaching quality monitoring and evaluation concept, and conform to the new era The construction of law major in Colleges and universities requires to solve the problem of weakening the value orientation of the teaching quality monitoring system of law major, so as to better form a comprehensive and systematic scientific teaching quality monitoring and evaluation incentive and constraint mechanism. To build a scientific monitoring system for the quality of practical teaching of law major, to evaluate and monitor the various links of practical teaching purposefully and systematically by using the methods of system theory and Cybernetics in combination with the practical teaching practice of the school, so as to make the quality of practical teaching achieve the expected purpose of a comprehensive system of mutual coordination and promotion.

2. Organization system of teaching quality monitoring

A three-level monitoring organization is composed of school, Institute (Department) and department (Teaching and Research Office). According to the management function, quality monitoring is implemented at different levels. The authoritative and permanent supervision organization of law school is the Teaching Steering Committee, the professional setting Committee, the teaching material Committee and the teaching supervision expert group. The academic affairs office is the center of supervision and implementation, which plays the role of organization, coordination, analysis and feedback. The Department (Department) is the entity of implementation of teaching and management, and also the most important organization of implementation of teaching quality monitoring. The teaching and research office is the most basic teaching unit. The smallest unit to implement teaching and management is also the most direct and key organization to implement teaching quality monitoring. The teaching quality control of law school is in the charge of the Teaching Steering Committee. The teaching management department of law school organizes and implements the daily teaching monitoring work according to the teaching quality monitoring regulations of the school and the specific requirements proposed by the Teaching Steering Committee. The college establishes a teaching quality monitoring group with the vice dean of teaching as the group leader, the director of the Department (Teaching and Research Office) and the teaching secretary of the college as the members, and the leaders in charge of student work and other relevant personnel of the college as participants. The teaching quality monitoring group of the college carries out the activities of students' evaluation of teaching and teachers' evaluation of teaching within the scope of the college according to the

information of students' evaluation of teaching and supervisors' evaluation of teaching and learning. The law school may also employ its teaching supervisors among its retired teachers to carry out its teaching supervision.

3. Method system of teaching quality monitoring

a. Teaching information monitoring

Through routine teaching order inspection, beginning, middle and end of term teaching inspection, Department (Department) teaching information feedback and student teaching information feedback and other conventional teaching information collection channels, timely understand and master the dynamic problems in teaching.

b. Teaching supervision and control

Carry out regular random supervision and feedback on all teaching activities, teaching links, various teaching management systems, teaching reform programs, etc. (3) special evaluation and monitoring. Through the evaluation of new majors, excellent courses, teaching materials, laboratories and test papers in the school, with the help of the auxiliary process monitoring of target monitoring, the diagnostic function of evaluation can be used to improve the quality of work.

4. System of teaching quality monitoring

a. Lecture system

The school leader, the supervision group, the department leader and the colleague unify the lecture system.

b. Teachers' teaching self-evaluation system

In the teaching inspection of each semester, the teacher fills in the self-assessment form of classroom teaching according to the teaching class, describes the basic teaching situation, students' learning situation and teaching reform suggestions objectively and truthfully, and provides reference for the teaching reform and learning style construction. After the examination of each course, the teacher fills in the examination quality analysis report to summarize the students' learning and teaching.

c. The system of teachers' peer lecture

Listening to each other among teachers plays an important role in improving teachers' teaching behavior, teaching art, professional level and teaching quality.

d. Online evaluation system for students

Online teaching evaluation can not only ensure the participation of students, but also realize the effective processing of teaching evaluation data. The school should insist on the students as the main body of the course teaching evaluation, and carry out the online evaluation once a semester. In order to ensure the participation of all students in the evaluation, the online evaluation should be linked with the students' course selection, and the evaluation should be carried out before the course selection. The school selects a certain proportion of teachers with low evaluation scores to follow up and listen to lessons, so as to help these teachers improve their teaching methods. At the same time, each semester through the form of questionnaire survey, the quality of teachers' teaching is evaluated.

e. Two way course selection system

Students choose teachers according to the class, on this basis, teachers also have the right to choose classes.

f. New teacher training and post assessment system

The pre job training system for new teachers is formulated from two levels of school and college to ensure that new teachers have a good starting point.

g. Academic warning system

We should continue to improve and implement the relevant system of 10 credit academic warning, 20 credit grade repetition warning and 30 Credit withdrawal warning, and strengthen the supervision of students' studies in the later period.

h. Elimination system of last place

Students who rank the last in the evaluation of teaching are suspended for further study, and those who rank the last again are transferred or transferred.

IV. Analysis of the main problems in the construction of the quality monitoring system for the training of law professionals

With the popularization of university education, the contradiction between the quantity growth and the quality decline of university personnel training becomes more and more prominent. If we simply pursue the benefits brought by the increase of quantity, and neglect the construction of teaching quality and basic teaching conditions, the supervision of teaching quality is virtual, and the evaluation of teaching quality is for evaluation, then the quality of talent training will inevitably decline. At present, there are still some problems and deficiencies in the quality monitoring system of legal personnel training in Colleges and universities.

A. the overall framework of talent training quality monitoring system needs to be improved

Lack of research on the target system and standard of teaching quality, only pay attention to the assessment of students' theoretical knowledge and classroom performance, and lack of assessment of students' application ability and basic quality; the second level college has not established the corresponding monitoring and guarantee mechanism of teaching quality, lack of the construction of a series of system related to the guarantee of teaching quality; there are teaching resources in the teaching operation and guarantee system There are some problems, such as lack of new professional teachers, insufficient number of Humanities and natural sciences courses to ensure the all-round development of students, lack of competition mechanism in Teachers' teaching, inflexible Title Incentive, lack of incentive and training mechanism for excellent teachers, failure to effectively mobilize teachers' enthusiasm in teaching, lack of effective monitoring on experimental courses, practice links, etc. The information feedback system of teaching quality monitoring system needs to be improved, and the feedback effectiveness needs to be improved.

B. Insufficient attention paid to the quality monitoring and evaluation of personnel training

School management at all levels repeatedly stressed the quality of personnel training, but the energy of ordinary teachers in teaching is obviously insufficient. At present, colleges and universities generally believe that teaching is the central link of school work, but the promotion and evaluation of teachers are mainly based on scientific research, or only assessment of scientific research work. The

emphasis on Teachers' scientific research results is higher than that on teaching. In the environment of "emphasizing scientific research and neglecting teaching", the teaching and scientific research time of university teachers are squeezed each other, so it is difficult to deal with the relationship between them. Of course, it is easy to quantify the scientific research achievements by using the standards such as the number of papers and monographs published; however, the standards for judging the teaching achievements are very vague. Young teachers face the real problems such as professional title and salary, bear more pressure on scientific research than old teachers, and tend to be impetuous and eager for quick success. In this case, the quality of undergraduate education is difficult to be guaranteed.

C. The concept of modern teaching quality needs to be strengthened

The traditional view of teaching quality only takes the examination results of students as the standard to measure the quality of personnel training. It pays more attention to knowledge teaching than ability training, and kills a large number of students with creative ability. According to a research report released in 2008 by McKinsey, a well-known management consulting company, only about one tenth of the millions of Chinese university graduates are qualified to work in foreign companies, compared with about a quarter in India. The research report points out that the combination of university education and industry needs in China is not close enough, and many Chinese universities adopt the teaching mode of emphasizing theory, relying on books and textbooks and tutors. Taking engineering students as an example, they rarely have the opportunity to participate in project practice and team work, lack of application skills and poor English level. Therefore, to speed up the reform of higher education teaching, change the concept of personnel training, strengthen the supervision of internal teaching quality in Colleges and universities, and cultivate application-oriented talents to meet the needs of the development of society, industry and enterprises, so that college graduates can win a place in the talent competition, is one of the important issues in the current reform of higher education and teaching.

D. Lack of self-restraint mechanism and strength of monitoring on talent training quality need to be strengthened

To evaluate the quality of talent training in Colleges and universities, it is more important to analyze whether college graduates are recognized by society, industry and enterprises, and whether they can create wealth for society, industry and enterprises. From this point of view, the monitoring of the quality of talent training in Colleges and universities is still lack of active self-restraint mechanism, there is a greater randomness and formalization. Some system documents have not been strictly implemented. And each teacher has its own teaching characteristics, often lack of comparability, and teachers' peers are afraid of "retaliation" due to low evaluation of others, which weakens the effectiveness of teaching quality monitoring. In addition, many aspects of the quality monitoring of talent training in Colleges and universities focus on the monitoring of teachers' classroom teaching activities, while the monitoring of the implementation of syllabus, case design, practice and students' learning situation is insufficient, lack of sufficient supervision and guidance.

E. The monitoring effect of classroom teaching quality needs to be improved

The operation of teaching quality monitoring of law undergraduate education is sometimes a mere formality, which fails to give full play to its goal of reflection, measurement and improvement. First of all, the evaluation results rely too much on the evaluation scores of students, ignoring the subjective factors in the evaluation, how to allocate more justice without in-depth research, and lack of scientific analysis and timely and effective feedback on the evaluation results. Secondly, both universities and teachers only pay attention to the evaluation results of teaching quality, ignoring the teaching quality monitoring system itself and the operation of the monitoring process. The rationality of the monitoring system and the fairness of the operation process are questioned. Finally, the monitoring results are only used for the benefit distribution of job evaluation, award evaluation and so on, but ignore the improvement of the shortcomings of the evaluated and the care for their future development, which is not conducive to the progress and sustainable development of teachers [5].

V. Measures to improve the quality monitoring and evaluation system of legal personnel training

A. Objectives and quality standards of quality monitoring for the training of legal professionals of scientific design

1. The goal of quality control in the training of legal professionals of scientific design

Reshape the core position of undergraduate teaching, adhere to the quality of personnel training oriented monitoring objectives. From the perspective of development trend, higher education in the future will pay more attention to the cultivation of students' ability to adapt to future employment, rather than being limited to a narrow professional field. Therefore, colleges and universities should strengthen the research of education and teaching, promote the development of a series of work, such as the optimization of specialty setting, the improvement of talent training program and curriculum reform, widely adopt modern education technology, reform traditional teaching methods, regularly revise required and elective courses, vigorously advocate general education, adhere to the unity of humanities education and science education, and cultivate interdisciplinary and interdisciplinary compound talents Talent, so that students can better adapt to the needs of society, enhance the competitiveness of employment.

2. Establish a comprehensive quality standard for personnel training

a. Establish a comprehensive quality standard for talent training

At the beginning of its establishment, the law major has attached great importance to the establishment of an efficient and orderly teaching management system, followed the spirit of "promoting construction by evaluation, promoting reform by evaluation", cooperated with the school's teaching management regulations and the college level teaching quality management and supervision system, and actively implemented the professional quality standards [4]. The quality standard of talent training is the code of management behavior for teachers and administrators. The process of undergraduate teaching quality assurance is to first determine the training objectives, formulate the training standards and design the training programs according to the

training objectives; use all available resources and conditions to implement the training programs through each link of the teaching process to achieve the training objectives; through quality monitoring, make the above quality activities in an effective monitoring state, and carry out quality analysis on the relevant information To achieve the purpose of continuous quality improvement. The quality assurance standard for undergraduate teaching in general institutions of higher learning issued by the Ministry of education includes four aspects: quality objectives, teaching resources, teaching process and quality management. Each aspect includes three elements, totaling 12 elements, and sets basic requirements for each element. According to this, colleges and universities can formulate the quality standards of talent training that are suitable for the characteristics of colleges and universities, and run them through the whole process of talent training, and effectively apply the evaluation results and feedback opinions to the revision of talent training programs and specific teaching links.

b. Fully implement the national teaching quality standards of law major

We will continue to innovate the training mechanism of legal talents, deepen the teaching reform of law majors, and improve the quality of legal talents training. In line with the idea of adhering to, reforming, adjusting and innovating the training of legal talents, we will follow the requirements of the outline of the national medium and long term education reform and development plan (2010-2020) and the opinions of the Ministry of education on comprehensively improving the quality of higher education, and earnestly implement them. The national standard reference framework for the teaching quality of law majors and the national standard for the teaching quality of law undergraduate majors in Colleges and universities. According to the positioning and characteristics of law schools, the teaching quality standards of law majors are formulated according to this standard, and the items in this standard are specified in detail.

c. Strictly implement the school's teaching quality standards

First of all, the formulation of the teaching plan is strict and serious. According to the relevant regulations of the school, teachers are required to draw up a complete and standardized syllabus before the commencement of the undergraduate course, and cannot start the course without the syllabus. The syllabus includes the teaching objectives of the course, the position and role of the course in the cultivation of students, the teaching contents and the distribution of class hours, the teaching methods and teaching means, and the assessment methods. The revision conforms to the requirements of the training objectives of the major, embodies the spirit of teaching reform, follows the teaching rules, is scientific, ideological and practical, and pays attention to the scientific knowledge, ideological education and quality education The combination of education has specific requirements for practical teaching. The revised syllabus or the new syllabus shall be approved by the academic committee of the college and submitted to the Academic Affairs Office for filing before implementation. The teacher has no right to change the syllabus without permission. Secondly, the teachers should be carefully determined and the teaching plan should be strictly implemented. The teaching and Research Office, academic committee and teaching supervision group should jointly

supervise the implementation. Thirdly, the teaching process management is strict. All courses are taught in accordance with the syllabus, and the teaching process is guided and supervised by the way of students' grading and evaluation, the supervision group and the leaders of the college, and the establishment of student grading system. There is a sound practice system and a long-term stable cooperative practice base, and the practical teaching effect is remarkable. The management of graduation thesis is standardized, which can be strictly controlled and managed according to the requirements of each link of graduation thesis of University and college. As for the filing and management of teaching documents and materials, the undergraduate teaching files and relevant materials of law major are complete, and the teaching syllabus, rules and regulations and other teaching materials are complete. Papers, examination paper approval form, graduation thesis, internship report, internship appraisal form, internship diary, academic year paper and other documents are bound neatly and stored in a standard and safe manner. The college has been rated as an excellent management unit in the inspection of the school's expert steering group for many years in a row.

B. Optimization of teaching quality assurance mode and system structure

1. Establish and improve teaching quality assurance mode and system structure

The composition of the quality monitoring system of legal personnel training in law school: the target system of quality monitoring of personnel training. Talent training target system: the main monitoring points are talent training target positioning, talent training mode, talent training program, discipline and professional transformation and development direction. Personnel training process system: the main monitoring points are the formulation and implementation of the teaching syllabus, the selection of teaching materials, the allocation of teachers, the quality of classroom teaching, the quality of practical teaching links, the reform of teaching content and means, assessment methods and test paper quality. Personnel training quality system: the main monitoring points are course qualification rate, award rate of various competitions, innovation ability and scientific research ability, graduation rate, degree award rate, postgraduate entrance examination rate, employment rate, employment level, employer evaluation, etc.

2. Establish and improve the teaching quality management system

a. Establish and improve the system of teaching quality monitoring

First of all, establish and implement the system of class attendance. We will implement a listening system that combines the leadership of the college, the supervision group, the department leaders and the peers. Teachers' teaching self-evaluation system. In the teaching inspection of each semester, the teacher fills in the self-assessment form of classroom teaching according to the teaching class, describes the basic teaching situation, students' learning situation and teaching reform suggestions objectively and truthfully, and provides reference for the teaching reform and learning style construction. After the examination of each course, the teacher fills in the examination quality analysis report to summarize the students' learning and teaching. The system of teachers' attending class together. Listening to each other among teachers plays an important role in improving

teachers' teaching behavior, teaching art, professional level and teaching quality. Secondly, we should implement a good online evaluation system for students. Online teaching evaluation can not only ensure the participation of students, but also realize the effective processing of teaching evaluation data. The school should insist on the students as the main body of the course teaching evaluation, and carry out the online evaluation once a semester. In order to ensure the participation of all students in the evaluation, the online evaluation should be linked with the students' course selection, and the evaluation should be carried out before the course selection. The school selects a certain proportion of teachers with low evaluation scores to follow up and listen to lessons, so as to help these teachers improve their teaching methods. At the same time, each semester through the form of questionnaire survey, the quality of teachers' teaching is evaluated. Moreover, the two-way course selection system is tried out: students choose teachers according to the class, on this basis, teachers also have the right to choose classes. New teacher training and assessment system. The pre job training system for new teachers is formulated from two levels of school and college to ensure that new teachers have a good starting point.

b. Strictly implement all rules and regulations of the school

Strictly regulate the management, revise the teaching plan and syllabus regularly, and summarize the management of examination and test paper regularly. Law school attaches great importance to the construction of teaching quality standards, forming a comprehensive and scientific quality standard system. The college establishes a comprehensive quality standard for personnel training. We will implement comprehensive teaching quality monitoring and establish a comprehensive quality standard for personnel training. The quality standard of talent training is the code of management behavior for teachers and administrators. The process of undergraduate teaching quality assurance is to first determine the training objectives, formulate the training standards and design the training programs according to the training objectives; use all available resources and conditions to implement the training programs through each link of the teaching process to achieve the training objectives; through quality monitoring, make the above quality activities in an effective monitoring state, and carry out quality analysis on the relevant information To achieve the purpose of continuous quality improvement. According to the quality assurance standard for undergraduate teaching in general institutions of higher learning issued by the Ministry of education, the quality objectives, teaching resources, teaching process and quality management are implemented in four aspects. Each aspect includes three elements, a total of 12 elements, and the basic requirements for each element are specified. The law school has formulated the quality standard of talent training suitable for the characteristics of the college, and has run it through the whole process of talent training, and has effectively applied the evaluation results and feedback opinions to the revision of talent training programs and specific teaching links. Under the Department of law (Law Teaching and Research Office), a teaching and research group was established to strengthen the research on the construction of law discipline and teaching reform, formulate the working procedures of the teaching and research group, and promote the reform of teaching methods and contents. Establish the

teaching and research group of basic law, civil and commercial law, economic law, international law and legal economics; carry out teaching and research activities regularly, strengthen the construction and implementation of teaching quality standards, and promote discipline construction and teaching.

c. Improve the organization, system and personnel implementation of the teaching quality assurance system

Establish and improve the organizational system of teaching quality monitoring. A three-level monitoring organization is composed of school, Institute (Department) and department (Teaching and Research Office). According to the management function, quality monitoring is implemented at different levels. The authoritative and permanent supervision organization of the college is the Teaching Steering Committee, the professional setting Committee, the teaching material Committee and the teaching supervision expert group. The academic affairs office is the center of monitoring and implementation, which plays the role of organization, coordination, analysis and feedback; the Department (Department) is the entity of implementing teaching and management, and the most important organization of implementing teaching quality monitoring; the teaching and research office is the grass-roots teaching unit, which is the implementation of teaching. The smallest unit of learning and management is also the key organization to implement teaching quality monitoring.

C. Improve the organization and personnel team construction of talent training quality monitoring

Although colleges and universities initially set up the relevant departments of teaching quality monitoring, which are supervised by the relevant departments of the academic affairs office, the personnel of the personnel training quality monitoring organization are mainly composed of the vice president in charge of teaching, the director of academic affairs and the deputy dean of teaching of each college, while the functional departments such as the personnel office, the student office and the recruitment and employment office are not enough to participate in the quality monitoring of personnel training. In order to ensure the scientificity and rationality of teaching management decision-making, and form vertical teaching quality monitoring subject stratification, a set of complete, scientific and strict rules and regulations are jointly formulated by teaching experts and teaching backbones with rich teaching experience, forming a mechanism for all staff to undertake the quality monitoring function of school personnel training. In the process of teaching quality monitoring, through the principle of "hierarchical management, division of responsibility, collaborative monitoring", the quality of talent training can be monitored step by step.

Optimize the incentive competition mechanism and improve the enthusiasm of teachers in teaching. In view of the serious problems of teachers' heavy research, teaching and academic bubbles, colleges and universities urgently need to improve the existing incentive mechanism, further highlight the teaching achievement evaluation, encourage full-time teachers to actively engage in undergraduate teaching, and strictly enforce the system of teaching for undergraduates. Especially in the evaluation and employment of teachers' professional and technical positions, the evaluation results of

teaching assessment must be taken as an important basis, and teachers who have obtained various teaching awards should be inclined. At the same time, colleges and universities should continue to strengthen the training of young teachers, create more opportunities, create a fairer and more relaxed environment, and make young teachers grow rapidly through various measures such as carrying out public overseas study training, increasing research start-up fees, and improving work and life treatment.

D. Establish and improve the quality monitoring mechanism of legal personnel training

1. Take an effective way to monitor the whole teaching process in real time

Law schools should regularly carry out various forms of teaching evaluation activities, check, evaluate and feed back the teaching quality, analyze and improve the feedback results, and establish a sound professional teaching quality monitoring system. The college and the teaching and Research Office shall establish and perfect the monitoring and guarantee system of teaching quality, find out the problems in teaching and improve them in time. Under the leadership of the dean in charge, in close cooperation with the director of the teaching and Research Office, the Teaching Committee, the deputy dean in charge of student work and the counselors of all grades, the major focuses on several key links, such as the opening, mid-term teaching inspection and final examination, and implements the monitoring of the normal and orderly development of teaching. At the beginning of each semester, students can learn about each course of this semester by means of student registration, class attendance and other methods, and solve problems in time. In the middle of the term, teachers and students have a variety of forms of symposiums to check the teaching, implement the teaching tasks of the next semester, and check the implementation of various teaching reform projects and curriculum construction projects. The final work is focused on the examination of students, the examination papers of teachers and the graduation thesis. The system of teaching and research section leaders, school teaching supervision group supervision and students' evaluation of teaching has played a good role in improving the teaching level of young teachers. The combination of centralized monitoring and daily monitoring. The centralized monitoring mainly includes: first, the inspection of preparatory work before and at the beginning of the school; second, the mid-term teaching inspection. In the middle of each semester, the centralized teaching inspection is carried out to monitor and evaluate the organization and arrangement of teaching process, the implementation of teaching plan, the implementation of each teaching link, etc.; thirdly, the final and year-end assessment. The relevant functional departments of law school conduct comprehensive assessment and evaluation on the teaching work and teaching quality of the school, and check the completion of relevant work. The daily monitoring mainly includes the irregular monitoring of the daily work and quality of the whole school and college teaching process, teaching organization, teaching discipline, etc. by the leading group of the college teaching quality monitoring.

2. Pay attention to the establishment and improvement of the teaching supervision system

To standardize teaching work, guarantee teaching quality, carry out teaching inspection, supervision, evaluation and

guidance, establish teaching supervision group (hereinafter referred to as teaching supervision group) of university law school, and formulate the measures in combination with the actual situation of law school. Under the leadership of the president and the vice president in charge of teaching, the teaching supervision group shall independently carry out its work in accordance with these measures, and perform its duties of teaching supervision fairly and impartially. The teaching supervision group has one group leader and several members. The members of the teaching supervision group shall have the following conditions: abide by the national constitution, laws and regulations, have good ideological and political quality, noble teachers' morality, strong sense of responsibility and fair handling of affairs; work in the front line of teaching or teaching management, have rich teaching or teaching management experience, generally have high-level professional title or doctor's degree; be engaged in teaching for more than 5 years, have dedication and strong discussion Ability of supervision and responsibility. Teachers who have obtained the honorary titles of famous teachers, moral pacesetters, teaching experts or young teaching experts at or above the school level shall be preferentially employed as teaching supervisors, which shall not be limited by the third paragraph of the preceding article. The leader and members of the teaching supervision group shall be discussed and deliberated by the school's leading body and appointed by the dean. Members of the teaching supervision group shall be appointed for a period of three years and may be re-elected. The work of the teaching supervision group adopts the system of group leader responsibility. The team leader is responsible for making the teaching supervision plan of each semester and organizing the members of the supervision group to carry out various teaching supervision activities. The teaching supervision group shall have a teaching supervision secretary, who shall be concurrently the teaching secretary of undergraduate and graduate students. The Secretary of teaching supervision assists the teaching supervision group to carry out all kinds of teaching supervision work and keep all kinds of teaching supervision files. The teaching supervision group shall perform the following duties: daily classroom teaching supervision, daily inspection and supervision of the classroom teaching of the teachers, put forward suggestions and suggestions to improve the teaching quality, feed back to the relevant teachers, and conduct follow-up guidance and inspection; the teaching supervision group shall listen to the class collectively no less than once every semester; each supervisor shall listen to the class no less than 8 times every semester; each supervisor shall listen to the class no less than 8 times every semester After the end of the class, the relevant supervision record form shall be filled in and submitted to the teaching supervision Secretary of the college for safekeeping at the end of the semester; the teaching supervision group shall convene or participate in a Student Symposium every semester to understand the students' needs and opinions on classroom teaching, which shall be summarized and sorted out by the teaching supervision secretary and fed back to the dean in charge of teaching. Special inspection and supervision: carry out special teaching supervision and inspection on experimental teaching, practical training, graduation thesis, teaching style and other related teaching activities; carry out special inspection and supervision on teaching reform projects, construction of excellent courses, experimental teaching, teaching links and teaching materials of teachers,

undergraduate graduation thesis, etc.; carry out special inspection and supervision on problems existing in teaching work of law school Investigation, organization and convening of teacher-student symposiums, to improve the quality of undergraduate teaching suggestions and countermeasures. Teaching evaluation and evaluation shall be carried out according to the unified deployment of the University and college; excellent teaching experience shall be promoted to help young teachers improve their teaching methods and improve their teaching level; other consultation, supervision, evaluation and guidance related to teaching shall be carried out. In the course of performing its duties, the teaching supervision group shall have the following rights: the right to enter the classroom and the laboratory at any time; the right to inspect the teacher's syllabus, teaching log, teaching plan, teaching courseware, examination syllabus. And put forward the power of inspection and evaluation opinions; with the approval of the leaders of the college, the power of checking the student status card and consulting the teaching management files of the college; the power of evaluating the teaching quality of the teachers; the power of one vote veto if the teaching effect fails to meet the conditions of evaluation of excellence and title. Exercise other powers in accordance with the relevant rules and regulations of the University and the authorization of the college's party and government joint meeting. The college takes the results of teaching supervision evaluation as an important reference for the evaluation of teachers' professional titles and the evaluation of the best teachers.

3. Establish a perfect mechanism for collecting and feedback of personnel training quality information

We should fully understand and master the overall quality level of talent training in Colleges and universities, find out the main factors that affect the improvement of talent training quality in time, and provide important decision-making basis for school leaders and secondary branch leaders to timely revise talent training plans, improve teaching links and continuously improve the quality of talent training. The mechanism of information collection and feedback should include routine teaching inspection feedback, teaching quality evaluation feedback, professional evaluation feedback, graduate social evaluation feedback, etc. It mainly includes three stages: collection and arrangement of teaching quality information and data, teaching quality diagnosis and evaluation, and correction of deviation of teaching activities. Therefore, the establishment of the whole process of the school teaching quality monitoring system, through the beginning of the semester, the middle of the semester, the end of the three stages of activities, to find out the problems in all aspects of the talent training process. It is specially emphasized here that colleges and universities should continue to improve the system of student teaching information staff, increase the team of student information staff and establish class and classroom logs in the quality monitoring system of talent training, so that the secondary branch can quickly understand the problems of students in class and the opinions of students on Teaching links and teaching management, give full play to the main role of students in teaching activities, and be firm Set up the education concept of "student oriented". In terms of teaching management, the teaching management team of law college is reasonable in structure and stable, and the academic affairs officers love their posts and are dedicated, practical and willing to work, diligent in learning and brave

in innovation. For many years, under the care and guidance of the leaders of the college, the undergraduate teaching office of the school of law has continuously strengthened the service consciousness of the members of the Department, paid attention to improving the professional quality, and actively cooperated with each department to carry out the teaching management work, so that the undergraduate teaching work of the school of law has been approved by the leaders, colleagues and students. The Secretary of the general Party branch, President, vice president, deputy secretary, head, deputy director, teaching secretary and other personnel of the law school constitute the teaching quality management team, carry out the internal supervision of teaching quality, ensure the improvement of teaching quality, and ensure the orderly operation of teaching order.

E. Establish a diversified talent training quality evaluation mechanism

Through the implementation of undergraduate teaching supervision, peer evaluation, student evaluation, teaching inspection, undergraduate teaching status evaluation and other systems, build a diversified quality evaluation mechanism; establish a talent training quality tracking investigation and evaluation system, and establish a social evaluation mechanism involving relevant industries and enterprises, covering a wide range of teachers, students, parents, employers and related industries and enterprises. Generally investigate and evaluate the quality of talent training in Colleges and universities, accept public supervision, and absorb the opinions and suggestions of various stakeholders on improving the quality of talent training in Colleges and universities, especially the opinions and suggestions of talent training base and talent practice base. The combination of self-evaluation and mutual evaluation. Self-evaluation refers to the evaluation of the teaching quality of the Department by the college. Mutual evaluation is to evaluate and grade teachers and students by secret ballot to evaluate each other's work (learning) attitude, work (learning) effect, etc.

Establish a sound and reasonable teaching quality evaluation system, strengthen scientific and effective teaching management, according to the characteristics of the discipline, formulate the corresponding curriculum reform plan and progress monitoring system for each course of law major, conduct real-time monitoring and management for each link in the plan, formulate each link to complete the setting of index parameters, refine the requirements and functions of each step in each process, and discover the plan in time And make real-time changes. Strictly implement the reasonable evaluation system, realize the planned improvement process, and gradually form a quantitative system. At the same time, we should strengthen the monitoring teaching, service teaching and other work, use scientific and effective means in teaching management, refine relevant regulations and practical operation procedures, put an end to the judgment and decision of human will, start from all aspects of teaching work to carry out all-round monitoring, at the same time, use human rules and regulations to achieve the support of teaching work and the guarantee of normal teaching work, and achieve management The effectiveness of. Strengthen the operation of service concept and actual behavior while strengthening management [6].

Improve self-evaluation and quality monitoring effect evaluation. The law school has established a perfect self-evaluation system of teaching and learning evaluation, and achieved good quality monitoring results. The college has formed a good atmosphere for all members to participate in quality monitoring. It comprehensively monitors and improves the teaching quality, standardizes the organization and process of each teaching link. According to the school's organization and management system, the college further standardizes the process of specialty construction and the formulation and improvement of training programs in specialty teaching, curriculum teaching management, assessment methods and teaching evaluation supervision system, and establishes a quality evaluation system. The college has formed a good atmosphere for all members to participate in quality monitoring. From the perspective of the overall effect of self-evaluation and quality monitoring, the college's teaching quality has been effectively guaranteed. Based on this standard, a quality monitoring and quality assurance system covering the above training objectives, training specifications, curriculum system, teaching specifications, professional teachers, teaching conditions, teaching effects and other indicators shall be established. According to the requirements of quality assurance objectives, the implementation standards of quality assurance for law major should be formulated, information feedback mechanism and regulation and improvement mechanism should be established, regular and systematic quality assessment should be carried out to ensure the effective monitoring of the whole process of teaching quality formation, and the continuous improvement of teaching quality for law major and the full realization of professional talent training objectives.

At present, we should pay special attention to the construction and operation of the evaluation system for the quality of practical teaching. The Academic Affairs Office of the University shall evaluate the overall practice teaching of law major. The Academic Affairs Office of the university may also entrust the practice teaching base and other employers or third-party evaluation institutions as the evaluation subjects to evaluate the practice teaching quality of law major. Through the diversification of the evaluation subjects outside the school, the evaluation results of practical teaching quality are more comprehensive and objective. The practical teaching steering committee and students of law major evaluate the practical courses of law teachers who are responsible for the practical teaching. Concerning the evaluation of practical teaching quality of practical teaching base, the law major applies for the staff of practical teaching base to participate in the evaluation work. The law teachers who undertake the practical teaching evaluate whether the students achieve the teaching purpose of the practical teaching course [7].

F. Improve the teaching quality improvement mechanism of law major

1. Strengthen the effect evaluation of quality improvement

The combination of qualitative monitoring and evaluation and quantitative monitoring and evaluation. Qualitative monitoring refers to the relevant information obtained through the monitoring and evaluation of specialized agencies and relevant departments. It is a kind of monitoring and evaluation information that can accurately reflect the

actual situation but the conclusion is relatively fuzzy. In order to reflect the comparability of monitoring and evaluation, quantitative monitoring is implemented at the same time. The school of law will test students' practical ability through spot check on graduation thesis (Design), experimental skills, educational practice, professional practice and other practical teaching links.

The law school should establish and perfect the procedure and mechanism of quality improvement, and evaluate the improvement effect timely. In the process of quality improvement, the problems and weak links in the external teaching evaluation have been comprehensively rectified and achieved good results. In view of the strong practical characteristics of law major, optimize the practical teaching curriculum system, innovate the practical experiment teaching methods, enrich the practical experiment teaching content, improve the practical experiment teaching links, and improve the comprehensive practical ability of students. Further strengthen the construction of talent training base and practice base outside the school. With the goal of cultivating high-quality applied talents, we should strengthen cooperation with the existing talent training base and talent practice base, consolidate the basis of cooperation, innovate the content of cooperation, improve the communication channels and coordination mechanisms between schools and enterprises, and close cooperation.

2. Reform and improve the ways and methods of quality improvement

Law school regularly analyzes the existing problems of teaching quality and makes improvement measures. Establish a good teaching and learning style. As a kind of cultural activity, education should not seek immediate success and instant benefit, or make false. Law school has always attached great importance to promoting the construction of teachers' morality and style of study, as well as the establishment and cultivation of students' correct style of study, so as to create a loving, dedicated, practical and conscientious style of teaching and education in the school, as well as a good style of study that respects teachers, values morality, and is honest and trustworthy. We will increase the introduction of talents, solve the problem of teacher shortage, and further improve the quality of teachers. Further optimize the teaching conditions, improve the lack of experimental facilities and equipment, and increase the investment of teaching funds.

G. Improve the quality monitoring and evaluation information utilization mechanism of law major

1. Improve the construction of the basic teaching status database

According to the unified requirements of the teaching database information collection of the academic affairs office, the school of law establishes a system of tracking investigation and statistical analysis of the information that can reflect the teaching quality. Law school has established a dynamic feedback system of teaching quality information network. In order to perfect and improve the teaching, we should know the feedback of students to the courses they teach.

2. Improve the mechanism of quality information statistics, analysis and feedback

Timely collect and report undergraduate teaching status data to ensure the authenticity and reliability of

undergraduate teaching status data. Establish a perfect mechanism of collecting and feedback on the quality information of personnel training, fully understand and master the overall quality level of personnel training in Colleges and universities, timely find out the main factors affecting the quality improvement of personnel training, and provide important decision-making basis for school leaders and leaders of secondary colleges to timely revise personnel training plans, improve teaching links and continuously improve the quality of personnel training.

3. Quality information disclosure and annual quality report

The information of teaching quality should be made public in time, and the annual quality report should be written to provide scientific basis for improving the monitoring of teaching quality. The teaching quality monitoring and guarantee information shall be disclosed in time, fed back in time, and followed up with improvement; the annual quality report shall be regularly written to comprehensively summarize and analyze the operation, achievements, problems and Countermeasures of the teaching quality guarantee system, which shall be an important scientific basis for improving the teaching quality guarantee system and strengthening the teaching quality monitoring.

4. Implementation of feedback from school supervision group

The law school actively cooperates with the statistics and feedback of teaching quality information of the school's academic affairs office. The school strictly implements the school's lecture and evaluation system, and earnestly absorbs the teaching improvement suggestions and opinions put forward by the school's teaching supervision group. Evaluate teachers' morality and style by listening to class. At the end of each semester, the students must evaluate the teachers. The college summarizes and analyzes the teaching work in a timely manner based on the results of students' evaluation, analyzes the records of the teaching supervision group, and focuses on strengthening the monitoring of the teaching quality of professional compulsory courses.

5. Improve the results utilization and processing mechanism of teaching quality monitoring and evaluation

The law major in Colleges and universities should make effective use of the evaluation results of practical teaching quality and play its core role in driving the improvement of practical teaching quality; colleges and universities can link the evaluation results of practical teaching quality with the promotion and remuneration of teachers, so as to encourage and restrain teachers to attach importance to practical teaching; colleges and universities can establish cooperation among the participation in practical teaching, practical ability, students' curriculum examination, graduation thesis, etc. With the same mechanism, to encourage and restrain students to attach importance to practical teaching and improve practical innovation ability [8]. At the beginning of each semester, feedback the evaluation results of the previous semester to the teacher. Record, reward and punishment of teaching quality monitoring and evaluation results. The teaching evaluation and monitoring results of each semester will be recorded in the teacher's teaching performance manual. The annual teaching quality monitoring results are the important basis for the promotion

of professional titles and post appointment. The monitoring results are linked with the application of teaching research projects and teaching awards.

H. Comprehensively and accurately evaluate the implementation effect of the quality monitoring and evaluation system for the whole process of personnel education

Performance evaluation should examine whether it can achieve the goal of improving the quality of higher education of law major, and closely focus on the talent training goal of undergraduate education of law major in Colleges and universities. It can further guarantee the improvement of teaching quality monitoring system, ensure the quality of law teaching and improve the effectiveness of teaching. Performance evaluation should examine whether it can reach the goal of improving the training level of law professionals, and build a set of teaching quality monitoring system centered on Teachers' sustainable development and students' learning input. From the perspective of school running ability, teachers' level and students' employment prospect, the training of law professionals should be oriented to the cultivation of high-quality, strong ability and practice oriented applied law undergraduate talents, instead of taking the discipline foundation of law majors in key universities to cultivate students' relatively broad disciplines. While focusing on the cultivation of students' practical ability, it should also pay more attention to students' theoretical scientific research Or the way to cultivate the ability of teaching. In performance evaluation, it is necessary to investigate whether the goal of improving the teaching quality management level of law major is achieved, establish a scientific classroom quality monitoring and evaluation system, and establish a teaching quality standard, which is conducive to the direct and effective monitoring of the teaching quality of law; establish a legal teaching quality standard and monitoring system, which is also conducive to the self-evaluation of teaching quality, so as to further improve the law Quality of learning and education. Performance evaluation should examine whether it can achieve the goal of effective connection between law education and employment, and strengthen the monitoring of practical teaching quality evaluation, which can better provide applied legal talents for social development. Based on the goal of application-oriented personnel training at undergraduate level, combined with its own actual situation, strengthen the monitoring of classroom teaching quality, pay attention to the training of students' professional skills, and further promote the match between the training goal of law professionals and employment needs.

To sum up, the construction of teaching quality monitoring system of law major in Colleges and universities should pay attention to the monitoring and control of teaching preparation, teaching process, teaching structure and other links in Law Classroom Teaching and practice teaching according to the predetermined standards and in certain ways, methods and means, so as to ensure that the teaching quality of law major reaches the expected goal. Based on the connotation of the teaching quality monitoring system of law major, combined with the current positioning of the education of law major in China and the quality standards of

law teaching in Colleges and universities, this paper explores the path to build the teaching quality monitoring system of law major in Colleges and universities from the training goal of law major talents in Colleges and universities. The construction of the teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law major in Colleges and universities is conducive to the improvement of the teaching quality monitoring system and the improvement of the teaching quality, so as to better complete the 13th five year plan of the construction of law major in Colleges and universities. According to the training plan and requirements of law professionals, starting from the training objectives of law professionals in Colleges and universities, the construction of teaching quality monitoring and evaluation system of law majors is essential to improve the quality of law talents training, which is conducive to ensuring the quality of law professionals training and ensuring that law talents meet the quality standards of law teaching.

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